

Tailored Methodology based on Vapor Phase Polymerization to Manufacture PEDOT/CNT Scaffolds for Tissue Engineering

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16 KEYWORDS: Carbon nanotubes, PEDOT, vapor phase
17 polymerization, conductive polymers, 3D scaffold, tissue
18 engineering, astrocytes
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25 ABSTRACT. 3D Scaffolds with tailored stiffness, porosity and
26 conductive properties are particularly important in tissue
27 engineering for electroactive cell attachment, proliferation
28 and vascularization. Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) and poly(3,4-
29 ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) have been extensively used
30 separately as neural interfaces showing excellent results.
31 Herein, we combine both materials and manufacture 3D
32 structures composed exclusively of PEDOT and CNTs using a
33 methodology based on Vapor Phase Polymerization (VPP) of
34 EDOT onto a CNT/sugar composite. Such a strategy presents
35 versatility to produce porous scaffolds, after leaching out
36 the sugar grains, with different ratios of polymer/CNT, and
37 controllable and tunable electrical and mechanical
38 properties. The resulting 3D structures show Young's Modulus
39 typical of soft materials (20-50 kPa), as well as high
40 electrical conductivity, which may play an important role
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3 for electroactive cell growth. The conductive PEDOT/CNT
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5 porous scaffolds present high biocompatibility after 3 and
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7 6 days of C8-D1A astrocytes incubation.
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Introduction

Traumatic spinal cord injury afflicts approximately 180,000 people worldwide each year.¹⁻³ Within the first stages after the injury, neurons and glia in the trauma site lose function, which is then extended to the surrounding tissue. Consequently, necrotic cells around the cavity form a scar, inhibiting growth and generating a strong insulating barrier that blocks the communication between the nearby healthy cells.⁴ Innovative solutions for such injuries require the development of materials able to prevent this natural process. Such implantable materials must fulfill very specific characteristics, such as porosity to allow nutrient flow, conductivity to enhance the electroactive cellular growth, similar mechanical properties as the tissue of interest and biocompatibility to support cellular growth and attachment.⁵

Tissue engineering is focused on the development of the ideal implants to regenerate or replace the damaged tissue within a dysfunctional zone. Large number of publications have reported how cells grow and interact in planar dimensions,⁵ although the human body represents a very complex three-dimensional cellular net, far from the bidimensional *in vitro* plate assays. Such a need to produce materials that simulate the complex matrix of the living systems set the 2D films aside to pave the way to 3D structures.⁶ Tridimensional scaffolds stand out for their increase in structural complexity, surface area, effective

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3 volume, and degree of porosity, thus providing gradients of
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5 nutrients and oxygen. Regarding electroactive cells, it has
6
7 already been demonstrated that nerves, bones, muscle
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9 tissues, cardiac cells, and mesenchymal stem cells are
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11 sensitive to electrical materials and electrical stimuli,⁷⁻
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13 ¹⁰ thus pointing conductive polymers out (CP) as potential
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15 materials for their culture, recording and stimulation.^{11,12}
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17 They possess electrical and optical properties similar to
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19 semiconductors, although their versatility, synthesis,
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21 biocompatibility and affordability are more attractive than
22
23 common metals. Poly (3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) is
24
25 the most used CP for a large number of applications, from
26
27 energy storage or organic transistors to biomedical devices
28
29 with living tissues.¹³⁻¹⁷ Commercial dispersions of PEDOT:PSS
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31 were already used to manufacture three dimensional foams for
32
33 bioelectronic applications, showing ideal mechanical
34
35 properties and conductivity for implants. The resulting
36
37 devices were evaluated for organic electrochemical
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39 transistors, to analyze the culture of 3T3-L1s cell and to
40
41 induce reorganization of proteins depending on PEDOT:PSS
42
43 oxidized state.¹⁸ As well, PEDOT:PSS platforms were tested
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45 for bone tissue engineering, demonstrating successful
46
47 differentiation of osteogenic precursor cells (MC3T3-E1).¹⁹
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49 However, the presence of PSS produces delamination and
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51 decomposition of the manufactured films or coatings, making
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53 the replacement of the dopant a required need in biological
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3 applications. Recently, Mantione *et al.* presented PEDOT
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5 dispersions based on the natural polymers GlycosAminoGlycan,
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7 which reduced the acidity of the residual sulfonate protons
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9 in PSS and improved the biocompatibility rate of long-term
10
11 implants.²⁰ Recent studies used PEDOT:XanthanGum 3D scaffolds
12
13 with tunable porosity and mechanical properties to monitor
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15 MDCK II eGFP cells growth.²¹ On the other hand, only one
16
17 recent study reported the use of Vapor Phase Polymerization
18
19 (VPP) to produce PEDOT and polypyrrole (PPy) 3D structures
20
21 *in situ*, using polystyrene microparticles as template for
22
23 the final interconnected pores.²²
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28 Carbon Nanoforms are ideally suited for interaction with
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30 electroactive cells.²³ In particular, Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs)
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32 have attracted tremendous interest in the past decade due to
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34 their outstanding properties.²⁴ CNTs are distinguished by
35
36 their excellent electrical and thermal conductivity,
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38 lightweight, mechanical properties and elasticity.²⁵ CNT films
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40 due to their nanotube morphology and electrical properties
41
42 have been used for stimulation of neuron cells from the NG108
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44 cell line, primary rat peripheral and hippocampal neurons.²⁶
45
46 Such studies showed that CNTs can boost the growth and
47
48 function of neurons, evoking postsynaptic responses on
49
50 hippocampal neurons, thus demonstrating potential for their
51
52 electrical coupling.²⁷ Other electroactive tissues, as the
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54 heart, have shown similar results.²⁸⁻³⁰ Polydimethylsiloxane
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56 (PDMS)/CNT scaffolds were manufactured to translate all
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3 previous studies performed on 2D films to a more complex and
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5 closer to real 3D structures. Those foams resulted a genuine
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7 platform to grow and percolate neurons and neuroglia, linking
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9 the activity of living neurons networks.³¹ Subsequently,
10
11 Usmani *et al.* presented a very promising *in vitro* study where
12
13 spinal cord explants were cultured on a sponge of CNTs
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15 producing spontaneous regrowth of the neurite within the
16
17 tridimensional network, which supported the reconnection of
18
19 the spinal cord segments.¹⁰ Those porous 3D PDMS/CNT
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21 scaffolds biocompatibility was also assessed *in vivo*,
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23 showing high potential to exploit the use of 3D CNTs-hybrids
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25 in the area of regenerative medicine.³²
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30 The combination of carbon nanomaterials and conductive
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32 polymers represents a powerful tool to generate biohybrid
33
34 materials able to promote tissue regeneration, to record
35
36 information and stimulation.³³ We have previously developed
37
38 a manufacturing method based on VPP, which allowed the
39
40 modulation of the ratio PPy/CNT, their mechanical
41
42 properties, porosity and conductivity.³⁴ In the present work,
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44 we use a similar methodology based on VPP to develop a
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46 hybridized material composed uniquely of PEDOT and CNT. Its
47
48 different chemical and physical properties, such as low
49
50 volatility, made it a challenge to manufacture
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52 tridimensional structures, thus the initial methodology has
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54 been modified to succeed. The resulting materials have been
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56 tested as biological platforms culturing C8-astrocytes,
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3 obtaining spread cell over the cultured structure. C8-
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5 astrocyte morphology was also evaluated using microscopic
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7 techniques, which showed good cellular interconnectivity.
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10 11 12 **Experimental**

13 14 ***Materials and Methods***

15
16 Carbon Nanotubes (CNT, >95%) were purchased from Nanoamor
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18 Inc. (Stock# 1237YJS: inner diameter 5-10 nm; outside
19
20 diameter 20-30 nm; length 0.5-2 μm). (3,4-
21
22 ethylenedioxythiophene) (EDOT; 98%) and iron (III) p-toluene
23
24 sulphonate hexahydrated ($\text{Fe}(\text{Ts})_3$, technical grade) were
25
26 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Iron (III) Chloride
27
28 hexahydrated (FeCl_3) was ordered from Fisher. Ethanol
29
30 (synthesis grade) was purchased from Carlo Erba Reagents
31
32 SAS. All reagents and solvents were used as received with no
33
34 further purification.
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39 Thermogravimetric analyses were performed under air
40
41 ($25\text{ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ flow rate) using a TGA Discovery (TA
42
43 Instruments). The samples were equilibrated at 100°C for 20
44
45 min and then heated at a rate of $10^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, in the range
46
47 from 100°C to 800°C . X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)
48
49 measurements were performed using a SPECS SAGE HR 100 system
50
51 spectrometer. A Mg $\text{K}\alpha$ (1253.6 eV) X-ray source was employed
52
53 operating at 12.5kV, at 8 and 10mA. The take-off angle was
54
55 90° and operating pressure was $8\cdot 10^{-8}$ mbar. Quantitative
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3 analysis of spectra was carried out using the Casa XPS 2.3
4
5 software.

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7 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) measurements were
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9 performed on JEOL JSM-6490LV at 15kV, running in a point by
10
11 point scanning mode. Micro-computed tomography (μ CT) was
12
13 used to quantify the porosity of the scaffolds. High
14
15 resolution micro-CT scans were performed on a SkyScan 1172
16
17 μ CT system (Bruker μ CT, Kontich, Belgium) at an energy and
18
19 intensity level corresponding to 33 kV voltage and 204 μ A
20
21 current for 1202 projections. Particle analysis toolbox in
22
23 ImageJ was used to determine the pore size distribution of
24
25 the scaffolds. Image processing protocol has been developed
26
27 to assess scaffolds' surface porosity, pore size
28
29 distribution and internal canalizations. Transmission
30
31 Electron Microscope (TEM) was carried out on JEOL JEM-2100F
32
33 model EM-20014, which features a 200 kV Field Emission Gun
34
35 (Schottky) "FEG" and an Ultra High Resolution Pole Piece
36
37 "UHR". Mechanical characterization was performed with a
38
39 Mecmesin MultiTest 2.5-i dynamic mechanical analyzer, using
40
41 a 50N load cell and Teflon-covered steel plates as holders.
42
43 The conductivity was evaluated through the electrochemical
44
45 impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using frequencies in the range
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47 from 0.1 to 1.000.000 Hz, with an electrochemical workstation
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49 Autolab MSTAT204 Potentiostat/Galvanostat.
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57 Mouse astrocyte C8-D1A cell line was purchased from ATCC-
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59 LGC and cultured in phenol red-free DMEM media (GIBCO)
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3 completed with 2 mM L-glutamine (Gibco), 100 U·mL⁻¹
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5 penicilline, 100 µg·mL⁻¹ streptomycin (Gibco), 1mM sodium
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7 pyruvate and 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum
8
9 (Gibco). The PBS buffer was purchased in tablets and prepared
10
11 following manufacturer procedures (Sigma-Aldrich),
12
13 corresponding to 10 mM phosphate buffer containing 137 mM
14
15 NaCl and 2.7 mM KCl at pH 7.4.
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21 ***3D scaffolds synthesis and characterization***

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23 The 3D scaffolds were produced through a multi-stage
24
25 process similar to the previously reported in our group.^{31,34}
26
27 250 mg of crystal sucrose were mashed and sifted through two
28
29 sieves with mesh sizes of 100 µm and 250 µm, respectively
30
31 (Fisher Scientific Inc.). Crystal sugar grains in the middle
32
33 fraction were collected, ensuring a grain size under 250 µm
34
35 and above 100 µm. CNTs (15 mg) and the sieved sucrose (500
36
37 mg) were mixed and shaken overnight. Then, 7% of oxidant
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39 (Fe(Ts) or FeCl₃) were incorporated and blended until
40
41 obtaining a homogeneous powder. Finally, 5 µL of MilliQ water
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43 were added and mixed. The resulting black blend was
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45 introduced inside a hollow plastic cylinder (Ø=5 mm) and
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47 compacted from both sides to form a cylindrical-shape
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49 template, which was then hanged with a thread inside a
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51 Schlenk flask. Subsequently, 0.4 mL of EDOT monomer were
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53 introduced at the bottom of the flask and the VPP was carried
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55 out under vacuum, varying two conditions: temperature (120°C
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3 and 140°C), and time of reaction (6h and overnight). Once
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5 the polymerization was completed, the cylinder was immersed
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7 overnight into MilliQ water to dissolve the sucrose and the
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9 excess of oxidant, resulting in a self-standing architecture
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11 with interconnected micro-channels and holes. The scaffold
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13 was cleaned with ethanol for five days in a Soxhlet system
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15 until complete removal of iron byproducts and free PEDOT
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17 oligomers. Dynamic decay of iron and chlorine in the system
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19 after Soxhlet cleaning was evaluated using XPS.
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23 ***Compressive modulus testing***

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25 Prior to mechanical testing, the scaffolds were soaked in
26
27 Milli-Q water for 1-2 min, and the excess of water was
28
29 carefully removed with a piece of Kimwipes®. Uniaxial
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31 compressive tests were performed under ambient conditions to
32
33 the wet scaffold since it represents a more similar
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35 biological environment, at a rate of 15 mm·min⁻¹, until
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37 reaching a 90% compressive strain. The extent of the
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39 deformation was measured by relating the measured height
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41 displacement at each point of the analysis with the
42
43 scaffolds' initial height (strain, in %). The obtained force
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45 curve was normalized to the specimens' initial diameter
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47 (stress, in kPa). Young's Modulus was then obtained as the
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49 slope of the stress/strain curve of the linear elastic
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51 section in the initial stages (typically from 15 to 40%
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53 strain in our case). At least 4-5 repetitions of each sample
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55 were measured.
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Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

The morphology on the scaffold's surface was analyzed by SEM. The samples were sliced in 2 mm thickness and evaluated in different magnifications. The sample was mounted on an aluminum holder with double-sided carbon tape.

Micro-computed Tomography (μ CT)

Scaffolds were isolated from the background, using a thresholding procedure that was specific to this material. The values to segment the scaffold from background were optimized comparing the 2D grey scale image of a single slice with the threshold image. In this way, binary images were created and porosity values for each slice were assessed (see example in Figure S1). Porosity values were determined as the percentage of pores' area with respect to the total area. Since both scaffolds had some imperfections (big pores, $d > 500 \mu\text{m}$) these regions or slices were discarded for the analysis. The analyzed areas in both samples are shown in Figure S1: the selected region for the first sample was between the slices 300 (Rec0300) and 655 (Rec0655) and between the slices 285 (Rec0285) and 650 (Rec0650) for the second. The material was highly homogeneous within the selected region for analyses, thus the porosity was calculated in 14 randomly selected slices ($n=14$) for the first sample, and 16 randomly selected slices ($n=16$) for the second.

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3 μ CT images were binarized using an optimized threshold and
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5 subjected to processing steps such as dilation, erosion and
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7 watershedding. To analyze the pore distribution, the area of
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9 each pore was measured, and the equation of a circle was
10
11 used to estimate an approximate value of the diameter of the
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13 pore, according to equation 1:
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$$15 \quad \text{Pores} = 2x\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{\text{circle}}}{\pi}}\right) \quad (1)$$

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20 Due to the high homogeneity of the system, the pore size
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22 distribution was calculated in n=10 2D-images randomly
23
24 selected along the 3D object.
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26 ***Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)***

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29 Intimate relationship between PEDOT and CNT was evaluated
30
31 using TEM studies. Samples were prepared by adding a single
32
33 drop (0.5 μ L) of the aqueous solution (ca. 0.1 mg·mL⁻¹ in
34
35 milliQ water) of PEDOT/CNT powder, obtained by grinding the
36
37 scaffolds, onto a copper grid coated with a carbon film
38
39 (Electron Microscopy Sciences). The grid was left to dry
40
41 under air for several hours at room temperature.
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44 ***Conductivity measurements***

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47 Relative conductivity between PDMS/CNT and PEDOT/CNT
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49 scaffolds was evaluated using Impedance Electrochemical
50
51 Spectroscopy (EIS). To carry out the measurement, a homemade
52
53 device was developed (Figure S2). The scaffolds were cut
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55 into cylinders of 5 x 5 mm (LxD), immersed in phosphate-
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57 buffered saline (PBS, 10 mM) and degassed for 5 minutes to
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3 ensure the complete permeation of the inner porous structure.
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5 Then, scaffolds were placed inside a PDMS container with few
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7 drops of 10 mM of PBS buffer solution. Two coplanar gold
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9 electrodes were placed in a sandwich conformation to complete
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11 the full structure and ensure the constant contact and
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13 electric flow within the 3D scaffold along the experiment.
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16 ***Biocompatibility assay***

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18 Before the in vitro assays, the scaffolds were dipped in
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20 MilliQ water several times in order to ensure the removal of
21
22 ethanol from the cleaning step. Then, they were left to dry
23
24 in air and cut into thin disks of 2mm thickness. PDMS/CNT
25
26 disks were cleaned under low-pressure oxygen plasma for 6
27
28 min (Pico Plasma Cleaner, Diener electronic) each side. Then,
29
30 all the scaffolds were UV-sterilized on each side for 20
31
32 min.
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37 *Cell culture and counting.* C8-D1A cells were cultured in
38
39 complete media at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ in tissue culture-treated
40
41 75 cm²-flasks (Nunc). For cell passage, cells were detached
42
43 from the flasks by incubation at 37 °C with trypsin-EDTA
44
45 solution 1X (2.5 g porcine trypsin and 0.2 g EDTA·4Na per
46
47 liter of Hanks' Balanced Salt, Sigma) and spun at 103 RCF
48
49 for 5 min; the obtained pellet was resuspended in 1 ml of
50
51 complete media and disaggregated. For cell counting, the
52
53 cell suspension was diluted 1:10 in PBS and 1:2 in the
54
55 exclusion dye Trypan Blue solution (0.4% in 0.81% sodium
56
57 chloride and 0.06% potassium phosphate, dibasic, Sigma). 10
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3 μL of the diluted cell suspension was counted in a
4
5 haemocytometer chamber under transmitted light in an
6
7 inverted microscope (DMIL, Leica).
8

9
10 All the 3D scaffolds were placed in a 96-well sterile plate
11
12 (Costar) and incubated in 200 μL complete media for 1h at 37
13
14 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO_2 . For cell seeding, the media was removed by
15
16 aspiration and 20-50 μl complete media containing $5 \cdot 10^5$ C8-
17
18 D1A cells were seeded onto the scaffolds. The wells were
19
20 filled by slowly adding 150 μL complete media and incubated
21
22 for 3 and 6 days at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO_2 .
23
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25
26 *LDH assay.* The viability of cells grown on the scaffolds
27
28 was evaluated with the modified LDH CytoTOX96 Non-
29
30 Radioactive Cytotoxicity Assay kit (Promega) reported by
31
32 Ali-Boucetta *et al.*³⁵ For cell lysis, scaffolds were
33
34 transferred to a 96-well U bottom plate and mechanically
35
36 disrupted by smashing after addition of 150 μL of PBS
37
38 containing 9% Triton X-100 (lysis buffer, LB). Then, the
39
40 samples were frozen at -80°C for 30 min, defrosted for 20
41
42 min at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and disrupted again. The CNT-PEDOT-based
43
44 material was separated by centrifugation at 1000 G for 10
45
46 min at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and supernatants were transferred to empty wells.
47
48 For the LDH detection, 50 μL of each supernatant was mixed
49
50 with 50 μL substrate mix and, after 4 min, the reaction was
51
52 terminated by the addition of 50 μL of stop solution.
53
54 Absorbance measurements at 492 nm were taken in a micro plate
55
56 spectrophotometer (GeniosPro, Tecan). Positive control
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3 diluted in LB 1:5000 was included as an internal control
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5 (not shown), and LB alone was used as negative control (not
6
7 shown). All the collected data is represented as means of
8
9 quadruplicates \pm SD. Student's *t* test was performed to draw
10
11 statistical comparisons between two treatment groups.
12
13 Differences were considered statistically significant at *p*
14
15 < 0.05 .
16
17

18
19 *Fluorescence staining of viable cells for microscopy.*
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21 Calcein-AM (Molecular Probes) staining was performed to
22
23 fluorescently label living cells. The scaffolds with cells
24
25 were transferred to empty wells and incubated at 37 °C for
26
27 30 min with 200 μ L of complete media containing 2.5 μ g·ml⁻¹
28
29 of Calcein-AM (Molecular Probes).
30
31

32
33 *F-actin stain for cell morphology imaging.* The scaffolds
34
35 incubated with cells were transferred to empty wells, washed
36
37 once with 200 μ L PBS, fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS
38
39 for 20 min at 20 °C, and washed twice with PBS. Then, the
40
41 cells in the scaffolds were permeabilized with 0.2% Triton
42
43 X-100 in PBS for 20 min at 37 °C. For cell F-actin filament
44
45 staining, the scaffolds were incubated at 37 °C for 30 min
46
47 in 200 μ L of ActinGreen488 (1:10, Molecular Probes) in 0.1%
48
49 Tween-20 PBS and washed twice with PBS before imaging.
50
51

52
53 *Confocal imaging.* Scaffolds with ActinGreen or Calcein-AM
54
55 stained cells were placed in a 50 mm-diameter #1.5 optical
56
57 glass-bottom-petri dish (Mattek) and a drop of PBS alone or
58
59 media containing 2.5 μ g·ml⁻¹ Calcein-AM was added,
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1
2
3 respectively. Images were taken in a laser scanning
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5 microscope (lsm880 AxioObserver, Zeiss) employing excitation
6
7 at 633 nm and detection between 615-670 nm in the reflection
8
9 mode for scaffold imaging, and excitation at 488 nm with
10
11 detection between 500-615 nm for Calcein-AM stained cells or
12
13 ActinGreen488 stained cells. For live imaging, a microscope
14
15 insert chamber was employed at 37 °C, 5% CO₂ and 100%
16
17 humidity. Each image stack consisted of 55 dual-channel
18
19 optical sections that were acquired at optimal intervals of
20
21 2 μm to reach a 100 μm-optical Z section with the Plan-
22
23 Apochromat 20x/0.8 M27 objective. ZEN software was employed
24
25 to generate a maximum intensity projection view from each Z-
26
27 stack image. Single dual-channel images of 1μm optical
28
29 section at higher magnifications using the Plan-Apochromat
30
31 63x/1.40 Oil DIC M27 objective were also collected.
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SEM imaging of the cell morphology inside the scaffolds

37
38
39 After cell culture, dehydration of the samples with an
40
41 ethanol in deionized water gradient (60%, 70%, 80%, 90%, and
42
43 100%) was carried out, each for 1 h at room temperature.
44
45 Finally, a second dehydration was performed with a
46
47 hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) in ethanol gradient solutions
48
49 (30%, 50%, 70%, 90%, 100%) using 30 minutes incubation for
50
51 each step. After 1 hour in HMDS 100% samples were air-dried,
52
53 sputter-coated with gold (Alto 1000, Gatan Inc.), and
54
55 visualized by SEM operated in secondary electron detection
56
57 mode.
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Results and discussion

Manufacture and composition of PEDOT/CNT porous scaffolds by VPP

Vapor phase polymerization (VPP) is commonly employed to deposit thin film layers of conductive polymers such as PEDOT or PPy onto non-conductive substrates to provide electrical conductivity. In a pioneering work, Winter-Jensen and co-workers determined that iron-based catalysts, in particular iron (III) tosylate, yields the highest conductive bidimensional PEDOT films.³⁶ Afterwards, many studies demonstrated that other reaction conditions, such as additives, temperature, time and amount of oxidant, have also a crucial effect on the final conductivity, which can exceed $1000 \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$.³⁷ In particular, a change in the temperature produces remarkable changes in the morphology of PEDOT, leading to an effect on the intercalation of the polymer chains and, thus, changes in the conductivity.^{38,39} We hypothesized that such conditions have a similar effect and behavior for the coating of PEDOT in a 3D structure. Therefore, our first goal was to analyze and optimize the reaction conditions not only to obtain highly conductive devices, but also to produce self-standing tridimensional PEDOT/CNTs scaffolds.

Figure 1 describes the general synthetic procedure to manufacture VPP scaffolds. Briefly, a sucrose-CNTs-oxidant

1
2
3 template was hanged inside a sealed tube containing EDOT
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5 monomer. As usual in VPP methods, the temperature was
6
7 increased, and the polymerization took place inside the
8
9 template where the EDOT vapor reacts with the oxidant. In
10
11 the final step, the porous PEDOT/CNT template was produced
12
13 by immersing the material in water and dissolving the sugar
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15 grains and the oxidant impurities. The porosity was estimated
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17 using a given weight of sucrose with specific granulometry
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19 between 100-250 μm as porogen. The conditions for the EDOT
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21 gas reaction with the oxidant were established in terms of
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23 time (6 h and overnight) and temperature (120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 140
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25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). It is worth noting that lower temperatures and shorter
26
27 times lead to collapse of scaffolds upon removal of sucrose,
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29 suggesting that not enough polymer was produced to hold the
30
31 entire structure. Since EDOT presents a low volatility
32
33 capacity (vapor pressure of 0.278 mmHg at 24 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), the VPP was
34
35 performed under vacuum. The kind and amount of oxidant
36
37 $\text{Fe}(\text{Ts})_3$ or FeCl_3 (adding 20 mg, 40 mg or 80 mg) was also
38
39 evaluated. However, only the scaffolds polymerized using 20
40
41 mg of FeCl_3 were stable keeping the 3D structure after the
42
43 cleaning step. This fact can be explained due to the more
44
45 powerful oxidant ability of FeCl_3 when compared to $\text{Fe}(\text{Ts})_3$;
46
47 furthermore, FeCl_3 has shown excellent results in the
48
49 previously synthesized PPy/CNTs 3D scaffolds.³⁴ On the other
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51 side, we postulate that larger quantities of oxidant hinder
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53 the polymerization due to the high humidity from the hydrated
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3 oxidant. As in previous works, Fabretto *et al.* pointed out
4 that additional water absorption in PEDOT polymerization
5 produces an increase in the formation of crystallite regions
6 within the oxidant layer, which are not able to participate
7 in an effective polymerization of EDOT.^{40,41} The complete
8 removal of Fe and Cl was confirmed by the lack of the
9 corresponding signals in the XPS analyses (see Figure S3).
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33 **Figure 1.** General scheme to manufacture PEDOT/CNT scaffolds:
34 template formed using sugar grains as porogen or sacrificial
35 template, CNTs and the oxidant; polymerization of PEDOT
36 through VPP; and washing with water and ethanol to remove
37 the sugar, reagents and side products.
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48 TGA was used to evaluate the ratio of PEDOT and CNT for
49 each preparation conditions. The resulting plots show two
50 well-separated degradation curves (Figure 2a and first
51 derivative curves in Figure S4): a first one between 100–500
52 °C, corresponding to the polymer loss, and a second starting
53 around 500 °C that corresponds to the CNT degradation. The
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amount of PEDOT polymerized was estimated in terms of percentage of weight loss per gram of sample at 500 °C, right before the degradation of CNTs begins, as shown in Figure 2a. The scaffolds' composition was determined between 42 and 68 wt% of PEDOT. According to the results collected in Table S1, there is an increase in the amount of PEDOT polymerized with time and/or temperature. The major effect was observed with a change in the temperature: an increase of 20 °C gives rise to *ca.* 25% more PEDOT deposition, while an increase in time from 6 h to overnight, results only in a 6% increase of PEDOT synthesized. These facts suggest that almost all the polymerization occurs within the first six hours of reaction. Additionally, we also corroborate that the PEDOT polymerization was homogeneous along the whole scaffolds by the analysis of several sections of the structure (see TGA plot in Figure S5).

Figure 2. a) TGA plot under air and b) Young's Modulus (wet) of the scaffolds synthesized in different conditions

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3 (n=5). Increase in time and temperature of synthesis yields
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5 to higher amount of PEDOT deposited and higher YM.
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10 ***Mechanical properties of the PEDOT/CNT scaffolds***

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12 Compression tests of the wet scaffolds were performed to
13
14 evaluate the Young's Modulus (YM's) of the manufactured
15
16 scaffolds. No swelling behavior was observed. The results,
17
18 reported in Figure 2b, show that the stiffness of the
19
20 material increases with the time and temperature of
21
22 polymerization, which are intimately correlated with the
23
24 amount of polymer deposited within the scaffold (see Table
25
26 S1 and Figure 2a). Interestingly, short periods of time, *i.*
27
28 *e.* 6 h of reaction, and/or lower temperatures, *i. e.* 120 °C,
29
30 results in similar YM's in the range of 20-30 kPa. Meanwhile,
31
32 high temperatures and large times of polymerization (140 °C
33
34 overnight) yields to more rigid scaffolds with the highest
35
36 YM's values, *ca.* 50kPa. Such values are close to the ones
37
38 reported for the spinal cord, thus suggesting good potential
39
40 for these scaffolds in spinal cord tissue engineering.^{42,43}
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48 ***Morphology of 3D CNT/PEDOT porous Scaffolds***

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50 Cells cultured on 3D structures exhibit behaviors more
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52 similar to *in vivo* conditions than cells cultured on 2D
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54 substrates. This is the reason why in 3D structures porosity
55
56 is a very important parameter to mimic the real environment
57
58 of biological tissues. In general, an increase in the number
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3 and size of pores, or the interconnectivity, usually leads
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5 to improved ECM secretion, cell infiltration, tissue
6
7 ingrowth, and molecular delivery.⁵
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10 Electron microscopy techniques were used to study the
11
12 number and size of pores upon removal of sucrose, used as
13
14 porogen or sacrificial template. The produced macropores
15
16 inside the polymeric scaffold, of irregular shapes mimicking
17
18 living tissue's irregular geometries, have been analyzed by
19
20 SEM. Images in Figure 3 reveal a homogeneous porous and
21
22 wrinkled morphology, plenty of interconnected holes and
23
24 folds. In particular, two kinds of surface can be
25
26 differentiated in the morphology of a hole: one smooth, which
27
28 may be related to PEDOT, and one coarse with a brush-like
29
30 shape placed in the frame of the cavities, which might
31
32 correspond to disorganized assemblies of CNTs, as confirmed
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34 upon observing at higher magnifications. No differences were
35
36 observed between the scaffolds synthesized by different
37
38 conditions, as shown in Figure S6. Moreover, the morphology
39
40 of the template before the sucrose dissolution was also
41
42 analyzed and the planar surface with absence of holes
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44 observed (see Figure S7) confirmed that PEDOT has completely
45
46 filled the empty spaces within the sucrose template.
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Figure 3. SEM micrographs of the 3D scaffolds (synthesized overnight at 140°C) that show the homogeneous micro-porosity. CNT are distributed over the polymeric surface, as distinguished in high magnification images.

Furthermore, micro-computed tomography (μ CT) was used to quantify the micro-porosity of two PEDOT/CNT scaffolds and analyze its internal 3D structure (Figure 4). The analyzed areas in both samples are shown in Figure S1. The surface porosity value of these nanocomposite scaffolds was found to be $45.01 \pm 2.86\%$ ($n=14$ slices) in the first sample and $47.54 \pm 4.09\%$ ($n=16$ slices) in the second one. This means that close to 45% of the sample's area corresponds to pores and 55% to matter. Note the small standard deviation among slices, which reflects the homogeneity of the object and supports the random selection of a finite number of 2D slices for image analysis. In addition, the analysis of μ CT images determined a structure formed mostly of macropores, composed of sizes between 20–300 μm . Two samples with different manufacture method conditions have been analyzed, and no significant differences between both pore size distributions were appreciated. As seen in Figure 4d, around 25% of the total pores are meso/micro pores, composing of pore size

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3 below 50 μm , almost 60% between 50 and 100 μm , around 20%
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5 between 100 and 150 μm and less than 7% above 150 μm (see
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7 Figure S8 for a higher size resolution histogram).
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37 **Figure 4.** **a)** Transversal μCT binarized image (2D), where
38 pores are represented in black color and matter (scaffold)
39 in white. **b)** Whole scaffold's 3D volume rendered image. **c)**
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41 3D illustration of scaffold's pore distribution; pores are
42 represented in red color and matter in white. **d)** Pore size
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44 distribution of two PEDOT/CNT scaffolds' synthesized at
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46 different conditions (sample #1: 140 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight, $n=14$;
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48 sample #2: 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight, $n=16$). Note that there are no
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50 significant differences between samples.
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5 TEM was employed to study the disposition and interaction
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7 between the polymer and the CNTs in the tridimensional
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9 nanostructure. PEDOT can polymerize in several nanometric
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11 forms, like nanorods, nanowires or nanoparticles, among
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13 others, depending on the polymerization conditions.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ In
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15 our case, as shown in Figure 5, we can distinguish between
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17 three sub-structures: (i) thin tubes with diameters around
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19 15-20 nm, corresponding to naked CNTs; (ii) thick tubes,
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21 which are assumed to be PEDOT/CNT hybrids with the polymer
22
23 wrapping the cylindrical structures; and (iii) polymer film
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25 agglomerates, determined as PEDOT. TEM revealed that most of
26
27 the CNT present in the scaffold are coated with the polymer,
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29 increasing the diameter up to 60 nm. It is worth noting that
30
31 such heterogeneity may be responsible for the scaffold's
32
33 structural integrity as the local agglomerates of polymer
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35 and polymer-wrapped CNT would underpin the whole structure.
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37 We hypothesize that the polymerization around CNT is mainly
38
39 achieved through the non-covalent π - π stacking of the
40
41 aromatic polymer backbone and the surface of the nanotubes.
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43 Such electrostatic interaction between conductive polymers
44
45 through non-covalent functionalization has already been
46
47 observed.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ In principle, there could be covalent
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49 attachment of PEDOT to the CNTs. As a matter of fact,
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51 extensive functionalization of CNTs leads to loss of the
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53 electronic properties. Since we retain high values of
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3 conductivity, we tend to believe that we have little or no
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5 reaction between PEDOT and MWNTs.⁵⁰
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26 **Figure 5.** Interaction analyses of the nanotubes and the
27 polymer *via* TEM micrographs of the CNT/PEDOT materials
28 obtained. Note that some nanotubes increase in diameter due
29 to the coating of the polymer, while in other regions small
30 films of PEDOT helps in the cohesion of the whole structure
31 and keep the tridimensionality.
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43 ***Electrical properties of 3D PEDOT/CNT scaffolds***

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45 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is a very
46 powerful tool to evaluate the three-dimensional conductivity
47 of the entire scaffold without destroying the sample. In
48 contrast to classical electrochemical techniques that
49 measure the charges or electrode potentials as a function of
50 time, EIS generates a signal as a function of the frequency
51 at a constant potential. In addition, EIS provides a large
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3 number of variables (frequency, voltage, phase, current,
4 etc.), thus a large amount of information that can be used,
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6 for example, to monitor the cell growth and colonization.⁴⁷
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8 Such technique has already been used to evaluate the 3D
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10 conductivity in scaffolds composed of PEDOT used to support
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12 cellular activity.⁵¹⁻⁵⁴ Meanwhile, the conductive behavior of
13
14 porous carbon electrodes used in materials chemistry for
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16 water deionization or as supercapacitors, has been analyzed
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18 through Bode and Nyquist plots.⁵⁵
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23 Figure 6 shows the Bode plot of the 3D scaffolds analyzed.
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25 The scaffolds were cut to obtain cylinders ($\varnothing = 5$ mm) of 5
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27 mm height and placed inside the electrochemical cell
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29 compartment (see Methods) in contact with the two gold
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31 electrodes. The electrochemical impedance spectra were
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33 obtained in the frequency range between 0.1 Hz and 1000 kHz.
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35 As a reference, previously reported scaffolds composed of an
36
37 insulating polymer, PDMS/CNT, with equal dimensions were
38
39 also analyzed to evaluate the electrical contribution of
40
41 CNTs. Our results show that the impedance of PEDOT/CNT
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43 ($|Z_{\text{PEDOT/CNT}}| = 6$ k Ω) scaffolds at 0.1 Hz was approximately ten
44
45 times lower than that of PDMS/CNT ($|Z_{\text{PDMS/CNT}}| = 50$ k Ω), and one
46
47 order of magnitude lower than the naked electrode filled
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49 with electrolyte PBS solution ($|Z_{\text{PBS}}| = 90$ k Ω , see Figure S9).
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51 We hypothesize that the impedance behaviour of the PEDOT/CNT
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53 scaffolds might arise not only from the presence of the CNT
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55 or the PEDOT themselves, but also from the conductive bridges
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3 formed between the conjugated thiophene chains of the PEDOT
4 matrix and the CNT during the polymerization process.
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23 **Figure 6.** Conductivity measurement through impedance (solid
24 line) and phase angle (dashed line) analyses vs frequency
25 measurement of the scaffolds PEDOT/CNT (blue) and PDMS/CNT
26 (black).
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32 The Bode plot in Figure 6, shows that PEDOT/CNT scaffold
33 present two responses in the phase: a maximum near medium
34 frequencies, *ca.* 100 kHz, corresponding to a phase of 52°,
35 and a small shoulder at lower frequencies. At the same time,
36 PDMS/CNT present a band close to 10kHz, although the maximum
37 phase is placed at 62°. The PEDOT/CNT scaffolds' phase Bode
38 plot can be associated to a Randle circuit behavior due to
39 the electrons flow through the entire matrix.
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50 Additionally, according to the Nyquist plot (see Figure
51 S10), the phase movement shows a capacitance behaviour at
52 high frequencies and a resistor contribution (Phase = 0°) at
53 lower frequencies. In contrast, the PDMS/CNT scaffolds show
54 capacitor behavior at low frequencies. Furthermore, the
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3 porous morphology of the scaffolds allows for a significantly
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5 higher surface-to-volume ratio, resulting in low impedance
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7 that is promising for neural probe applications.
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10 11 12 ***In vitro biocompatibility of 3D PEDOT/CNT scaffolds*** 13

14 Mouse astrocytes C8-D1A were cultured on scaffolds for 3
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16 and 6 days and *in vitro* cytotoxicity was analyzed using a
17
18 modified Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) assay. This method has
19
20 been reported previously to circumvent all interactions
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22 between CNT and the insoluble formazan crystals formed in
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24 the commonly used 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-
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26 Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide (MTT) or conventional LDH
27
28 viability tests, and thus assessing the impact of CNT-based
29
30 material on cellular survival in a straightforward and
31
32 reliable manner.³⁵ The LDH activity signal of the cytosolic
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34 fraction was taken as a semiquantitative measurement of the
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36 number of surviving cells in the scaffolds. Once the cells
37
38 are lysed, the level of absorbance of the LDH product
39
40 correlates with the number of viable cells growing on the
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42 scaffolds. As all the scaffolds were seeded with the same
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44 number of astrocytes, differences would be attributed to the
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46 effect of the materials on cell survival. The previously
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48 reported PDMS/CNT was analyzed for comparison.
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55 In a first experiment, the effect of the different
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57 polymerization conditions employed was evaluated, *i.e.*
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59 different PEDOT/CNT ratios, and showed no significant
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3 differences between the different kind of scaffolds (see
4 Figure S11). In a second step, the PEDOT/CNT scaffolds were
5 compared with the previously synthesized PDMS/CNT scaffolds,
6 and, again, no significant differences in the absorbances
7 were observed (see Figure 7a). These facts demonstrate not
8 only the non-cytotoxicity of the different scaffolds
9 developed, but also that the scaffolds manufactured have a
10 positive impact on the C8-D1A growth yet in the first three
11 days of culture.
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43 **Figure 7. a)** *In vitro* LDH assay of C8-D1A astrocytes
44 cultivated for 3 days on scaffolds in the presence of 30%
45 CNTs. Maximum projection view of Z-stack images after **b)**
46 calcein-AM stain of viable cells (green) and **c)** the cell
47 membrane F-actin (yellow) staining of PEDOT/CNT scaffolds
48 after 3 days of culture. Merge view: stained cells (green or
49 yellow), scaffold (grey). Images are fluorescent and
50 reflection acquisitions for C8-D1A and scaffolds by confocal
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3 microscopy, respectively. **a)** All values are expressed as
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5 means \pm SD from 4 independent experiments ($n=3$). $P>0.05$,
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7 results are considered statistically non-significant by
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9 Student's t test.
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13 In addition, confocal imaging was employed to analyze the
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15 cellular attachment to the PEDOT/CNT scaffold. Only living
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17 cells were stained with calcein-AM in fluorescent green after
18
19 incubation in the scaffolds for 3 and 6 days. Furthermore,
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21 z-stacks showed certain degree of cell penetration within
22
23 the range of visualization allowed by the objective working
24
25 distance (up to 100 μm) through the pores of the scaffold
26
27 (see Figures S12 and S13). The images in Figure 7b and
28
29 Figures S12-S14 show high confluence of alive cells adhered
30
31 to the scaffold, even after 6 days *in vitro*. The adhesion
32
33 and proliferation of C8-D1A cells on PDMS/CNT scaffolds was
34
35 also evaluated with calcein-AM staining for comparison,
36
37 showing different growth behavior: astrocytes on PDMS/CNT
38
39 scaffolds tend to grow forming clusters of cells, as shown
40
41 in Figure 7b and Figures S12-S14, instead of spreading over
42
43 the whole surface, as with the PEDOT/CNT scaffolds. Cluster
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45 formation produce a less homogenous biological active
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47 surface onto the material, decreasing their own growth
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49 stretching and the long-distance communication between them,
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51 having an effect on their natural activity presumably.⁵⁶
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3 Furthermore, the morphology of the astrocytes was analyzed
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5 by staining their cytoskeleton with filamentous actin (F-
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7 actin, Figure 7c). Large elongations of the filamentous axons
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9 of the cells was observed, indicating the typical phenotype
10
11 of astrocytic cells. This is a clear indicator that the cells
12
13 keep their original function.
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16
17 SEM images of the cultured cells in Figure 8 confirmed that
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19 astrocytes maintain their normal morphology. Large
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21 elongations, as well as abundant cell-to-cell contacts
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23 (highlighted with green arrows), can be distinguished,
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25 suggesting the guidance and enhancement of the material
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27 during their growth and expansion, as previously reported.³³
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29 This observation not only confirms the low cytotoxicity of
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31 the material, but also let us anticipate that the cells are
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33 also able to maintain their function.
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47 **Figure 8.** SEM images of the astrocytes grown in the 3D
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49 PEDOT/CNT scaffolds for 3 days. Higher magnifications show
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51 the close interaction and adhesion of the astrocytic
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53 filaments to the scaffold.
54

55 56 57 **Conclusions** 58 59 60

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3 In this work, we have taken advantage of the VPP methodology
4 to manufacture 3D porous scaffolds composed uniquely of PEDOT
5 and CNT by using a sucrose template as sacrificial a porogen.
6
7 This procedure represents a powerful tool to manufacture
8 tridimensional scaffolds with controllable properties,
9 including the polymer composition, porosity, conductivity
10 and compressive toughness. The scaffolds' composition was
11 modulated from 42% to 68% of PEDOT through different
12 reactions conditions, as determined by TGA. Compressive
13 experiments revealed YM's in the range of 20-50 kPa, typical
14 values of soft systems. The resulting porosity, pore
15 diameters and homogeneity obtained after the sucrose removal
16 were analyzed using SEM and μ CT, confirming high homogeneity,
17 pore size mostly in the order of 50-100 μ m and excellent
18 interconnectivity between them. As well, EIS analyses showed
19 that the PEDOT/CNT scaffolds are highly conductive and have
20 impedances ten times below the previously reported PDMS/CNT.
21 Finally, high viability was demonstrated with the incubation
22 of astrocytes. Overall, our results illustrate how the
23 prepared scaffolds are suitable candidates for implants in
24 neural tissue.
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54 ASSOCIATED CONTENT

55 Supporting Information included.
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60 Present Addresses

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10 **Author Contributions**

11
12
13 The manuscript was written through contributions of all
14
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17 version of the manuscript.
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51 NanoBEAT.
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ABBREVIATIONS

VPP, Vapor Phase Polymerization; CNTs, Carbon; PEDOT, poly(3,4 ethylenedioxythiophene); CP, Conductive Polymers

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3 **For Table of Contents Use Only**
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5

23 **Title:** Tailored Methodology based on Vapor Phase
24 Polymerization to Manufacture PEDOT/CNT Scaffolds for
25
26 Tissue Engineering
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29
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Figure 2. a) TGA plot under air and b) Young's Modulus (wet) of the scaffolds synthesized in different conditions (n=5). Increase in time and temperature of synthesis yields to higher amount of PEDOT deposited and higher YM.

388x163mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 1. General scheme to manufacture PEDOT/CNT scaffolds: template formed using sugar grains as porogen or sacrificial template, CNTs and the oxidant; polymerization of PEDOT through VPP; and washing with water and ethanol to remove the sugar, reagents and side products.

328x114mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of the 3D scaffolds (synthesized overnight at 140°C) that show the homogeneous micro-porosity. CNT are distributed over the polymeric surface, as distinguished in high magnification images.

312x76mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 4. a) Transversal μ CT binarized image (2D), where pores are represented in black color and matter (scaffold) in white. b) Whole scaffold's 3D volume rendered image. c) 3D illustration of scaffold's pore distribution; pores are represented in red color and matter in white. d) Pore size distribution of two PEDOT/CNT scaffolds' synthesized at different conditions (sample #1: 140°C overnight, n=14; sample #2: 120°C overnight, n=16). Note that there are no significant differences between samples.

196x194mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 5. Interaction analyses of the nanotubes and the polymer via TEM micrographs of the CNT/PEDOT materials obtained. Note that some nanotubes increase in diameter due to the coating of the polymer, while in other regions small films of PEDOT helps in the cohesion of the whole structure and keep the tridimensionality.

158x83mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 6. Conductivity measurement through impedance (solid line) and phase angle (dashed line) analyses vs frequency measurement of the scaffolds PEDOT/CNT (blue) and PDMS/CNT (black).

208x123mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 7. a) In vitro LDH assay of C8-D1A astrocytes cultivated for 3 days on scaffolds in the presence of 30% CNTs. Maximum projection view of Z-stack images after b) calcein-AM stain of viable cells (green) and c) the cell membrane F-actin (yellow) staining of PEDOT/CNT scaffolds after 3 days of culture. Merge view: stained cells (green or yellow), scaffold (grey). Images are fluorescent and reflection acquisitions for C8-D1A and scaffolds by confocal microscopy, respectively. a) All values are expressed as means \pm SD from 4 independent experiments ($n=3$). $P>0.05$, results are considered statistically non-significant by Student's t test.

247x111mm (72 x 72 DPI)

Figure 8. SEM images of the astrocytes grown in the 3D PEDOT/CNT scaffolds for 3 days. Higher magnifications show the close interaction and adhesion of the astrocytic filaments to the scaffold.

268x65mm (72 x 72 DPI)